

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

A penal data analysis on the effects of climate variations on malaria incidences among children 0-5 years in Uganda

George Robert Okello ^{1,*}, Robert Wamala ², Hellen Namaweje ¹, Martin Mbonye Kayitale ¹ and Herbert Susan Sendege ³

¹ Department of Population Studies, College of Business and Management Sciences, Makerere University, P. O. Box 7062, Kampala, Uganda.

² Directorate of Research, Innovations and Partnership, Makerere University, P. O. Box 7062, Kampala, Uganda.

³ Department of Statistical Methods, College of Business and Management Sciences, Makerere University, P. O. Box 7062, Kampala, Uganda.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 27(03), 213-228

Publication history: Received on 20 July 2025; revised on 28 August 2025; accepted on 03 September 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.27.3.3122>

Abstract

Despite global reductions in malaria due to intensified interventions, it remains a major cause of hospitalizations and deaths among Ugandan children under five. Uganda's changing climate may be influencing malaria incidence in this vulnerable group. This study examined the relationship between climate variations and malaria prevalence among children under five across 13 Ugandan districts, selected for their high disease burden and susceptibility to climate change.

Using a retrospective research design and penalized data analysis, district-level random effects were incorporated into a negative binomial regression model. Results showed a positive association between malaria cases and minimum temperature (coefficient = 0.0333, $p < 0.0000$) as well as vegetation cover (NDVI, coefficient = 0.3240, $p < 0.0000$). Conversely, maximum temperature was negatively associated (coefficient = -0.0099, $p < 0.0000$). Rainfall was insignificant in the combined model but significant in separate analyses.

Regional variations emerged, with particularly high incidence in West Nile districts Yumbe (214), Adjumani (168), Koboko (150), and Karamoja's Kotido (141), Nabilatuk (196), and Napak (130). Findings highlight the influence of temperature and vegetation on malaria prevalence, underscoring the need for region-specific malaria control strategies that integrate climatic and environmental factors.

Keywords: Climate Variability; NDVI; Malaria; Rainfall; Temperature

1. Introduction

Almost half of the global population is vulnerable to malaria. In 2022, around 249 million individuals contracted malaria across 85 nations(1). That year, the disease resulted in roughly 608,000 fatalities(2),(3). Sub-Saharan Africa is responsible for approximately 93% of all malaria-related deaths worldwide(4). In 2020, this region accounted for 95% of malaria cases and 96% of deaths. Children under five represented about 80% of malaria fatalities in this region(5). There are geographical variations in malaria incidence, notably among sub-Saharan African countries, with Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of Congo contributing over 10% of the global malaria cases: Nigeria (31.9%), Democratic Republic of the Congo (13.2%), United Republic of Tanzania (4.1%), and Mozambique (3.8%) (Saba, 2022). Conversely, nations such as Burundi and Swaziland recorded less than 1% of malaria cases(6). Additionally, it is estimated that 96%

* Corresponding author: George Robert Okello

of the malaria deaths in Sub-Saharan Africa are among children under five years(7). Uganda ranks sixth worldwide and third in Africa in terms of malaria mortality, with 16 million cases and over 10,000 deaths reported each year(8). The Malaria Indicator Survey 2018-2019 revealed that 9% of children aged 0-59 months tested positive for malaria parasites (9). The same survey indicated an increase in malaria incidence among this age group from 3% to 12%. Furthermore, malaria incidence is nearly four times greater in rural areas (11%) compared to urban settings (3%). Regionally, Karamoja exhibited the highest malaria incidence at 34%, followed by West Nile at 22% and Busoga at 21%, while Kampala and Kigezi had the lowest incidence, each below 1%(10). Malaria places a substantial socio-economic burden on households in Uganda and on the national economy. Direct expenses, such as consultation fees, medication, transport, and care, are compounded by indirect costs like lost workdays, decreased productivity, and negative educational impacts. An average malaria episode costs households about \$26, totaling \$78 annually for families encountering three episodes, which is 3% of their income. Poor households in malaria-endemic areas may allocate up to 25% of their income on prevention and treatment, which exacerbates poverty levels. For children under five, the estimated annual economic impact is around \$614 million, of which \$57.7 million is attributed to direct medical costs(11). In addition to affecting individuals and households, malaria hinders national development by lowering agricultural and industrial output and deterring foreign investment(12). Severe cases of malaria can impair cognitive development in children by as much as 60%, thereby weakening human capital and adversely affecting Uganda's universal education initiatives(13). Campaigns to fight malaria through interventions such as insecticide-treated nets (ITNs), indoor residual spraying (IRS), and intermittent preventive treatments have made some headway. For example, the national malaria parasite incidence fell from 42% in 2009 to 9.1% in 2018, and the 2024 campaign distributed over 30 million ITNs nationwide(14). Nonetheless, malaria cases have been on the rise in more than 70 districts, indicating significant gaps in control strategies. Environmental factors, including increased temperatures, humidity, and modified rainfall patterns, further exacerbate malaria transmission dynamics, undermining the potency of existing interventions(15). Climate change is increasingly acknowledged as a major factor in the revival and spread of malaria in specific areas. Changes in environmental aspects such as temperature, rainfall, humidity, and the frequency of severe weather events create situations that can either promote or hinder malaria transmission(16). These alterations in environmental conditions can significantly affect the life cycle of Anopheles mosquitoes and the development of the Plasmodium parasite within them, ultimately impacting malaria rates and the geographical distribution of the disease(17). This study intends to explore the connection between climate variations and malaria occurrences in children aged 0-5 years in Uganda over an eight-year period from 2015 to 2022.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design

The research employed a retrospective longitudinal design. This was centered on verified malaria cases in children under five years old, along with climate factors such as maximum temperature, minimum temperature, and vegetation cover.

2.2. Data Sources

The study used secondary data from January 2015 to December 2022 as follows.

- Uganda National Meteorological Authority (UNMA), where we got data on climate variables such as rainfall and temperature
- Uganda Ministry of Health (MoH), where we got data on confirmed malaria cases among children under five years.
- Satellite Data (Vegetation Indices: NDVI), where we got data on vegetation cover

The above data can be obtained from the following links.

Table 1 Data Sources

Variable	Access Link
Vegetation (NDVI)	NASA Earth Data, Copernicus
Climate (Rainfall, Temp)	CHIRPS, WorldClim, ESGF
Malaria Incidence	WHO Malaria Data, DHIS2
Land Use/Cover	NASA EOSDIS

2.3. Study area

The research focused on four areas: West Nile, Karamoja, Ankole, and South-central. The choice of these regions was informed by the findings from the Uganda malaria indicator survey conducted in 2019, which indicated that West Nile and Karamoja experienced the highest rates of malaria. Additionally, the survey revealed that South Buganda and Ankole had the lowest rates of malaria among children under five years. The study considered thirteen districts in all four regions. These were selected based on the load of the malaria cases as reported by the Ministry of Health. Three districts were selected from each region: two with high loads and one with a lower load. As illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Area of study

Figure 2 Distribution of Health facilities under study

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of health facilities by their respective levels. The facilities are categorized according to the levels defined by the Ministry of Health. The analysis focused on four categories of health facilities: Hospitals, HCII (Health Center II), HCIII (Health Center III), and HCIV (Health Center IV). These facilities are responsible for reporting monthly health indicators to the Ministry of Health via DHIS2. Each level signifies a different tier within the healthcare system, offering distinct capabilities and services. As indicated in Table 2.1, the distribution includes 34 (2.9%) hospitals, 721 (51.7%) HCII facilities, 336 (39.5%) HCIII facilities, and 39 (5.8%) HCIV facilities.

2.4. Variables and their measurement

The research focused on confirmed malaria cases in children under five years as the dependent variable, while Vegetation Cover, Rainfall, and Temperature were treated as the independent variables.

Table 2 Summary of Variables and their Measurements

Variable	Measurement Method	Data Source	Units	Spatial Resolution
Dependent variable				
Malaria Incidence	Confirmed malaria cases among children under five years per health facility	Local Health Centers	Confirmed cases	
Independent variables				
Vegetation Cover	Derived from satellite reflectance (NIR and RED bands)	MODIS	NDVI (-1 to +1)	250m
Rainfall	Measured via satellite-based precipitation estimates and ground stations	CHIRPS, Weather Stations	mm (month)	0.05°
Temperature	Measured via satellite or ground-based meteorological stations	CHIRPS and Weather Stations	°C, minimum and maximum	0.1/9km

NIR- Near-Infrared, **RED**- Red region of the electromagnetic spectrum, **MODIS**- Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer, **NDVI**- Normalized Difference Vegetation Index; **CHIRPS**-Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data

2.5. Data Preparation and Standardization

Before merging the datasets, both the climate and malaria datasets were formatted to ensure compatibility regarding the same time frames and geographical areas. The climate and malaria information were synchronized to include the same duration, with both datasets compiled into monthly intervals across the study period from 2015 to 2022.

Additionally, both datasets were aligned to a unified coordinate system (latitude/longitude) to ensure precise spatial integration.

2.6. Data Analysis

This research employed panel data analysis. Panel data is characterized by information gathered from multiple subjects (districts) observed over a period(18). This methodology facilitates the examination of both time-related changes and variations across different sections. The primary outcome variable for this study was the aggregate number of confirmed malaria cases in children under the age of five. The panel data analysis framework accommodates variations within districts across time and differing characteristics between districts, providing a comprehensive perspective on malaria dynamics throughout the districts.

2.7. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics offered a deeper understanding of the data characteristics. Univariate analysis focused on examining the distribution, central tendency, and variability of individual variables. For climate-related variables such as temperature and rainfall, the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values were calculated. Trend analysis revealed seasonal patterns or temporal changes. With regards to malaria incidence, descriptive statistics and line graphs illustrated trends and distributions. Pearson correlation analysis evaluated the relationships among variables, yielding insights into their interdependencies and interactions.

2.8. Exploratory Analysis

A vital element of the negative binomial model is the dispersion parameter, which assesses the extent of variability or dispersion in malaria cases. A significantly greater than zero dispersion parameter signals overdispersion, supporting the choice of the negative binomial model instead of the Poisson model. By analyzing the dispersion parameter, researchers gain a clearer perspective on the inherent variability in the data, essential for precise modeling and prediction. The findings from this exploratory analysis highlighted which variables played the most critical roles in forecasting malaria cases, guiding the selection of variables for the final modeling phase. The final model is expected to include these significant variables, facilitating more accurate predictions or inferences concerning malaria incidence. The fitting of a basic negative binomial model during the exploratory phase was an essential step. It not only enhanced the understanding of the distribution and variability in malaria cases but also informed the choice of key variables for the final model. This comprehensive methodology guarantees that the concluding model effectively reflects the data and is capable of yielding meaningful insights for public health strategies and policy-making. **Inferential Analysis**

At the multivariate level, both Poisson and negative binomial models were constructed using confirmed malaria cases in children under five years old. This was carried out through random effects estimation. Initial tests, such as overdispersion using an auxiliary model and Hausman tests, guided the selection of the model. A divergence test was conducted to compare Poisson and negative binomial models to identify the best fit. Visual comparisons of observed data versus modeled distributions validated the chosen model, ensuring the reliability and validity of malaria dynamics analysis.

2.9. Negative Binomial Model

The analysis regarded the total count of confirmed malaria cases among children under five years old as count data, typically modeled via the Poisson distribution. However, in situations of overdispersion (where variance is greater than the mean), more sophisticated models are necessary. The Negative Binomial (NB) model, which introduces a parameter for additional variability, is often applied to over-dispersed count data. Alternative models include Quasi-Poisson, which modifies standard errors for over-dispersion, and Zero-Inflated models, which accommodate a surplus of zeros. Since there were no instances of zero malaria cases in any district throughout the months, zero-inflated models were disregarded. Considering the diverse climate conditions across districts, the Negative Binomial model was chosen for its capacity to manage over-dispersion. This study adhered to the model specifications proposed by noted authors in the field.

From the general representation of a classic linear model

$$Y = XB + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots 2.10$$

Where $Y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)^T$ is the n dimensional vector if the observed outcome variable; X , is the $n \times p$ design matrix where p is the number of parameters in the model; $B = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p)^T$ is a p dimensional vector of parameters including the constant term; and $\epsilon = (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \dots, \epsilon_n)^T$ is an n dimensional vector of the error term which represents the

random variation in the model. The model specification described above is based on several assumptions about the error term and the dependent variable, such as normality and constant variance. Violations of these assumptions necessitate modifications to the model, particularly in cases where the outcome variable is a count, as in the current study. In such situations, the concept of generalized linear modeling offers a valuable solution for the modeling process.

The generalized linear model concept is hinged on three key components, that is

The outcome variable comes from the distribution of the exponential family with $E(Y) = \mu$, and $Var(y) = \alpha(\phi)$. $var(\mu)$, where ϕ is a scale parameter and $\alpha(\cdot)$ is a function of ϕ that explains the random component.

$\eta = XB$, which is the systematic component examining the effect of all the covariate information on the response variable

$\eta = g(\mu)$ Where $g(\cdot)$ is known as the link function

The algebraic representation of the generalized linear model then becomes

$$g(Y) = \eta = XB \dots\dots\dots 2.11$$

The generalized model framework assumes that the outcome variable Y follows a distribution that belongs to the exponential family, which can be represented as below

$$f_Y(y, \theta, \phi) = \exp \left\{ \frac{[y\theta - b\theta]}{\alpha(\phi)} + c(y; \phi) \right\} \dots\dots\dots 2.12$$

In this case, ϕ it is referred to as the dispersion and θ as the canonical parameter. This analysis in this study assumed a modeling procedure of this nature, assuming a negative binomial link.

There are several ways that can be embedded in the above modeling procedure to cater for the variation of malaria cases across districts, these include accounting for either fixed or random effects during the analysis. Although both terms are crucial for handling the inherent heterogeneity in the data, fixed effects account for variations at the parameter level, estimating a specific parameter for every individual observation in the data. This, however, restrains the possibility of examining variations across the different groupings in the data. Accounting for random effects in the model presents a solution to this, as it enables estimation of variation across groups of interest (districts in this study). Including this in the estimation procedure in equation 2 generates equation 3 below, which was adopted at the modeling stage in this study

$$g(Y) = \eta = XB + ZU \dots\dots\dots 2.13$$

From Equation 3 above, ZU defines the variation across districts and is referred to as the random effects term in the analysis.

3. Results

Table 3 Distribution of health facilities by region

	Regions				
Health facilities	Ankole	Karamoja	South central	West Nile	Total
Hospitals	1	2	28	3	34
Health Centre IV	7	2	27	3	39
Health Centre III	43	17	220	56	336
Health Centre II	83	24	548	66	721
Total	134	45	823	128	1130

Table 3 presents the allocation of health facilities among the four regions. The South-Central Region leads with the highest number of facilities, totaling 823, which includes 28 hospitals, 27 Health Centre IVs, 220 Health Centre IIIs, and 548 Health Centre IIs. Conversely, the Karamoja Region contains the smallest number of facilities, with a total of 45, consisting of 2 hospitals, 2 Health Centre IVs, 17 Health Centre IIIs, and 24 Health Centre IIs. The Ankole Region has 134 facilities, which comprise 1 hospital, 7 Health Centre IVs, 43 Health Centre IIIs, and 83 Health Centre IIs, while the West Nile Region has a total of 128 facilities, including 3 hospitals, 3 Health Centre IVs, 56 Health Centre IIIs, and 66 Health Centre IIs. Altogether, the total number of health facilities across all regions is 1,130, highlighting a substantial concentration of resources in South Central and a more restricted availability in Karamoja.

Table 4 Distribution of study variables

Variable	No.	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max	Skewness
Confirmed Malaria	4,024,028	94.25	81.27	4	350	0.77
Rainfall	4,580,845.31	91.47	20.21	51.75	136.83	-0.01
Temperature Min	796,028.42	16.24	2.26	9.66	20.34	-1.21
Temperature Max	1,370,410.84	29.02	3.74	17.87	34.68	-0.92
NDVI	2,3031.8	0.50	0.07	0.33	0.65	-0.42

Table 4 presents summary statistics for various variables associated with malaria and environmental factors. It displays the count of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and skewness for each variable. Confirmed Malaria shows an average of 94.25 cases, with a standard deviation of 81.27, indicating significant variability in the number of malaria cases, and a positive skewness of 0.77, which points to a long right tail. Rainfall averages at 91.47 mm and has a standard deviation of 20.21 mm, with a skewness of -0.01, indicating that the data is nearly symmetrical. The minimum and maximum temperatures have averages of 16.24°C and 29.02°C, respectively, with negative skewness values of -1.21 and -0.92, suggesting that their distributions are more concentrated at the higher end. Lastly, NDVI records a mean of 0.50 with a standard deviation of 0.07 and a skewness of -0.42, indicating a mild negative skew, with values mainly clustered towards the upper range of the vegetation index.

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 5 Summary Statistics for Analysis Variables by District

	Average Malaria cases	Average Total rainfall amounts	Average Minimum Temperature	Average Maximum Temperature	Average NDVI
Adjumani	168	99.313	18.702	32.95	0.514
Bukomansimbi	28	98.255	16.710	26.98	0.556
Gomba	27	103.371	16.485	28.058	0.580
Isingiro	34	78.456	14.533	27.61	0.504
Kiruhura	16	78.702	14.738	27.239	0.515
Koboko	150	112.091	17.738	30.639	0.480
Kotido	141	64.08	16.367	30.716	0.351
Lwengo	36	97.415	16.491	27.539	0.487
Nabilatuk	196	82.832	17.131	32.34	0.435
Napak	130	81.135	16.675	31.329	0.407
Rwampara	6	61.739	10.294	19.749	0.411
Wakiso	60	118.267	18.106	27.896	0.464
Yumbe	214	102.461	18.576	32.199	0.499

Error! Reference source not found.5 shows considerable variation by districts: Yumbe and Nabilatuk have high malaria cases (214 and 196, respectively, while Rwampara has the lowest (6). Rainfall also varies, with Wakiso receiving the most, while Kotido has the least. Temperature ranges are broad, with higher temperatures generally observed in areas with more malaria cases, possibly indicating a relationship between these factors.

Table 6 Summary Statistics for Analysis Variables by year

	Average Malaria cases	Average Total rainfall amounts	Average Minimum Temperature	Average Maximum Temperature	Average NDVI
2015	77	91.879	16.105	30.019	0.523
2016	85	83.76	16.207	30.244	0.509
2017	84	91.899	16.213	30.284	0.512
2018	75	104.899	15.941	29.58	0.519
2019	88	108.216	16.504	29.678	0.528
2020	94	111.034	15.876	27.989	0.534
2021	87	87.04	17.973	26.876	0.51
2022	95	95.201	17.998	26.931	.4094

Table 6 presents summary statistics by year. From the table, the average number of malaria cases fluctuates, with a general increase observed from 2018 to 2022. Rainfall amounts also show variability, peaking in 2019 and 2020. The minimum temperature remains relatively stable, while the maximum temperature shows a gradual decline from 2016 onward. The NDVI values suggest slight changes in vegetation health, with a peak in 2020 followed by a decrease in subsequent years, potentially indicating variations in environmental conditions over time.

3.2. The relationship between rainfall, minimum temperature, maximum temperature, vegetation cover, and confirmed malaria cases among children under five years.

Here, we conducted a correlation analysis to assess the relationship between confirmed malaria cases among children under five years and rainfall, minimum and maximum temperature, and Vegetation cover, as shown in Table 7 Correlation Results7.

Table 7 Correlation Results

	Malaria cases	rainfall	Minimum Temperature	Maximum Temperature	Veg cover
Total Malaria cases	1.000				
Total rainfall amounts	0.080***	1.000			
Minimum Temperature	0.194***	0.328***	1.000		
Maximum Temperature	0.175***	0.019***	0.702***	1.000	
Vegetation cover	0.048***	0.355***	0.217***	0.130***	1.000

The data presented in Table 7 reveal noteworthy yet generally low correlations among the variables, emphasizing positive connections between climatic and environmental factors and instances of malaria. Malaria Cases exhibit weak positive correlations across all variables, with the strongest association being with Minimum Temperature (0.194), indicating a slight rise in malaria cases as minimum temperatures increase. The correlations with Maximum Temperature (0.175) and Rainfall (0.080) are less pronounced, while the link with Vegetation cover is the weakest (0.048), suggesting a minimal direct effect of vegetation health on malaria instances. Rainfall shows a moderate correlation with Vegetation cover (0.355) and Minimum Temperature (0.328), underscoring the impact of rainfall on

supporting vegetation health and affecting minimum temperatures. Minimum Temperature has the most robust correlation with Maximum Temperature (0.702), demonstrating their natural interdependence, along with a moderate correlation with Vegetation cover (0.217), highlighting its significance for vegetation health. In summary, while environmental factors influence malaria dynamics, the weak correlations indicate that other unmeasured factors could play a more substantial role. Overall, the correlations among the variables range from low to moderate, with the highest correlation found between Minimum and Maximum Temperatures (0.702). The relatively weak relationships of Malaria Cases with environmental factors like rainfall, temperatures, and Vegetation cover imply that these variables each contribute to explaining malaria dynamics independently, without redundant overlaps.

3.3. Climate variation and malaria using panel analysis

Table 8 Relationship between rainfall amounts and malaria cases

Malaria cases	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Total rainfall amounts	0.0007	0.0001	11.05	0.0000	0.0005	0.0007	***
Constant	0.0625	0.0085	7.35	0.0000	0.0458	0.0791	***
ln(alpha)	-0.0192	.345			-0.6953	0.6571	
ln(s)	3.3672	.44			2.5046	4.2298	***
Mean dependent var	85.850		SD dependent var		135.895		
Number of obs	44624		Chi-square		122.101		
Prob > chi2	0.000		Akaike crit. (AIC)		454433.758		
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

The positive coefficient (0.0007) suggests that as the total rainfall amounts increase, the number of malaria cases also increases. The relationship is statistically significant (p-value = 0.0000) at the 5% level of significance. The dispersion parameter (ln(alpha) = -0.0192) suggests that 2% of the variations in total malaria cases, but this variation was not significant. Overall, the regression analysis indicates a significant positive relationship between rainfall amounts and malaria cases, with a statistically significant model fit.

Table 9 Relationship between minimum temperature and malaria cases

Malaria Cases	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Minimum Temperature	0.025	0.001	17.09	0.0000	0.022	0.027	***
Constant	-0.281	0.025	-11.33	0.0000	-0.329	-0.232	***
Constant	0.052	0.347			-0.629	0.732	
Constant	3.483	0.436			2.628	4.339	
Mean dependent var	85.850		SD dependent var		135.895		
Number of obs	44624		Chi-square		292.199		
Prob > chi2	0.000		Akaike crit. (AIC)		454232.716		
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

Table 9 presents a regression analysis concerning malaria cases, indicating that the minimum temperature has a significant impact on malaria incidence, shown by a positive coefficient of 0.025 (p < 0.01), signifying that higher minimum temperatures correlate with an increase in malaria cases. The overall significance of the model is validated by a chi-square value of 292.199 (p < 0.001). The average number of malaria cases reported is 85.85, and the standard deviation is 135.895, demonstrating considerable variability in the dataset. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)

stands at 454,232.716, implying a good fit for the model. Several constant terms are included, with only the first being statistically significant, which likely indicates various model specifications or groupings.

Table 10 Relationship between maximum temperature and malaria cases

Malaria cases	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Maximum Temperature	0.0031	0.001	4.40	0.0000	0.002	0.004	***
Constant	0.0346	0.021	1.62	0.105	-0.007	0.077	
Constant	-0.0171	0.345			-0.688	0.665	
Constant	3.3786	0.44			2.517	4.24	
Mean dependent var	85.850		SD dependent var			135.895	
Number of obs	44624		Chi-square			19.327	
Prob > chi2	0.000		Akaike crit. (AIC)			454534.475	
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$							

Table 10 presents regression findings analyzing the impact of various factors on malaria cases, indicating a positive correlation between maximum temperature and malaria incidence (coefficient = 0.0031, $p = 0.0000$). The small standard error suggests that the estimates are precise, and the chi-square test indicates the overall significance of the model ($p < 0.001$). The average number of malaria cases is 85.85 with considerable variability (SD = 135.9), and the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) of 454,534.475 implies a good model fit. Some constant terms are included without significant effects, which may indicate different specifications of the model.

Table 11 Relationship between Vegetation cover and malaria cases

Malaria cases	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
NDVI	0.38635	0.0240	16.0900	0.0000	0.3393	0.4334	***
Constant	-0.0696	0.0138	-5.0400	0.0000	-0.0966	-0.0424	***
ln(alpha)	-0.0293	0.3446			-0.705	0.6463	
ln(s)	3.3455	0.4406			2.482	4.2091	**
Mean dependent var	85.850		SD dependent var			135.895	
Number of obs	44624		Chi-square			258.975	
Prob > chi2	0.000		Akaike crit. (AIC)			454291.604	
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$							

According to table 11, there is a positive correlation between vegetation cover and total malaria cases (coefficient = 0.38635), indicating that as vegetation cover increases, total malaria cases also tend to rise. This association is statistically significant (p -value = 0.0000) at the 5% significance level. The dispersion parameter ($1/\ln(\alpha) = -0.0293$) indicates that approximately 2% of the variation in total malaria cases can be attributed to changes in vegetation cover. Additionally, the parameter was negative and not significant, suggesting that there is no over-dispersion in malaria cases related to vegetation cover.

Table 12 below presents the results of the Poisson regression model as a preliminary step for testing for overdispersion.

Table 12 Poisson Regression Results Before testing overdispersion

Total Malaria cases	Coef.	Standard Error.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	
Total rainfall amounts	.001	0.000	141.06	0.000	0.001	0.001	
Min Temp	.122	0.000	433.73	0.000	0.121	0.122	
Max Temp	.066	0.000	430.74	0.000	0.066	0.067	
NDVI	.826	0.004	208.15	0.000	0.819	0.834	
Constant	-.191	0.007	-29.12	0.000	-0.204	-0.179	
Mean dependent var	85.850		SD dependent var		135.895		
Pseudo r-squared	0.122		Number of observations		44624		
Chi-square	709775.747		Prob > chi2		0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	5111444.737		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		5111488.268		
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$:							

Table 12 presents results from a Poisson regression model examining the relationship between Total Malaria Cases and the independent variables: Total Rainfall Amounts, Minimum temperature (Mini), Maximum temperature (Max), and NDVI. All independent variables are statistically significant at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$). The coefficients suggest that increases in Total Rainfall Amounts (0.001), Mini Temp (0.122), Max Temp (0.066), and NDVI (0.826) are positively associated with Total Malaria Cases. The model is statistically significant overall (Chi-square = 709775.747, $p < 0.001$). Following the above analysis, an auxiliary model was fitted to test for overdispersion, and the results are presented in Table 13 below.

Table 13 Results of the Overdispersion Test

Dispersion variable	Coef.	Standard Error.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
$\hat{y}^* = ((y - \hat{y})^2 - y) / \hat{y}$							
Predicted values $\sqrt{\hat{y}}$	1.948	0.097	20.090	0.000	1.758	2.138	***
Mean dependent var	231.482		SD dependent var		1907.201		
R-squared	0.009		Number of observations		44624		
F-test	403.415		Prob > F		0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	801014.550		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		801023.256		
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$:							

From Table 13 above, the coefficient for the auxiliary coefficient is 1.948, significantly greater than zero ($t = 20.09$, $p < 0.05$). The small p-value confirms that the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating overdispersion is present in the data. This implies that a standard Poisson regression may not be appropriate, and a model like the Negative Binomial regression, which accounts for overdispersion, would better fit the data.

4. Results for Inferential Statistics and discussion

Before model fitting, a Houseman test was conducted to assess the most suitable model between fixed and random effects models. Table 14 Housman Test Results for the Fixed and Random Effects Model14 presents the results of the houseman test.

Table 14 Housman Test Results for the Fixed and Random Effects Model

Variables	Coefficients		b-B	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
	Fixed Effects Model (b)	Random Effects Model (B)		
Total Rainfall Amounts	-1.75E-06	-1.51E-06	-2.37E-07	3.06E-07
Minimum Temperature	0.0340778	0.0341155	-0.0000377	
Maximum Temperature	-0.0099097	-0.0098976	-0.0000121	
Vegetation Cover	0.3139488	0.3137664	0.0001824	0.0001573

The Hausmann test results in Table 14 compare the coefficients derived from fixed effects and random effects models for various variables, revealing only slight differences in the estimates. For Total Rainfall, the difference is -2.37×10^{-7} , accompanied by a standard error of 3.06×10^{-7} , suggesting an insignificant variance. The differences for Minimum and Maximum Temperature are minimal (-0.0000377 and -0.0000121 , respectively), with no standard errors provided, possibly due to issues with collinearity. For NDVI, the difference stands at 0.0001824 , with a standard error of 0.0001573 , indicating a similarly negligible difference. These minor discrepancies suggest that the random effects model could be appropriate unless the Hausmann test statistic proves significant.

According to the results from the Hausmann test shown in Table 14, a negative binomial model including a random effects component was fitted to a combination of total rainfall amounts, temperature, and vegetation cover to evaluate their combined influence on total malaria cases. In a basic model, all three variables were significant. The following table displays the results of the complete model. This model incorporates district-level random effects and considers 44,624 observations across 13 districts. It is assumed that the district-level random effects adhere to a Beta distribution, which enables the model to account for unobserved heterogeneity among districts. The Wald χ^2 statistic of 341.20, with a p-value of 0.0000, indicates that the independent variables (Total rainfall amounts, Temperature, and Vegetation cover) are collectively significant in accounting for the variations in malaria cases. To address temporal changes in malaria incidence, time in years was utilized as the exposure variable.

A negative binomial model was applied to a combination of total rainfall amounts, temperature, and NDVI to investigate their joint effect on total malaria cases. All three variables proved significant in the simple model. The subsequent table outlines the results of the comprehensive model. By including total rainfall amounts, temperature, and NDVI, the model provides a thorough understanding of the elements impacting malaria cases. Total rainfall amounts can influence mosquito breeding sites, while temperature may affect the lifecycle of mosquitoes and the development of malaria parasites. NDVI, serving as a metric of vegetation greenness, can signify areas that are suitable habitats for mosquitoes.

4.1. Effects of climate variation on total confirmed malaria cases among children under five years.

Table 15 Model results for Negative Binomial Model

Total Malaria cases	Coef.	Standard Error.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf Interval]	Sig	
Total rainfall amounts	0.0000	0.0001	-0.0300	0.9770	0.0000	0.0000	
Minimum Temperature	0.0333	0.0019	17.60	0.0000	0.0296	0.03670	***
Maximum Temperature	-0.0099	0.0010	-9.48	0.0000	-0.0119	-0.0079	***
NDVI	0.3240	0.0195	16.59	0.0000	0.2857	0.3623	***
Constant	-7.9143	0.0272	-291.24	0.0000	-7.9675	-7.8610	***
ln(Year)	1.0000	Exposure					
ln(alpha)	0.0342	0.3467			-0.6452	0.7137	
ln(s)	3.4556	0.4373			2.5985	4.3127	***
alpha	1.0348	0.3587			0.5245	2.0415	***
s	31.6787	13.8525			13.4448	74.6418	***

Mean dependent var	85.850	SD dependent var	135.895
Number of observations	44624	Chi-square	575.596
Prob > chi2	0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)	453964.553
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$:			

From Table 15, each variable contributes uniquely to understanding the factors influencing malaria cases, with significant effects observed for temperature, NDVI, and scaling parameters.

The minimum temperature shows a significant positive correlation with malaria cases, as demonstrated by a coefficient of 0.0333 (p -value = 0.0000). This suggests that for each one-unit rise in minimum temperature, the expected number of malaria cases increases by around 0.0333 units, with other variables held constant. The 95% confidence interval for this effect is quite narrow, ranging from 0.0296 to 0.0367, indicating a precise estimate and high reliability of the findings. The statistical significance of this relationship, evidenced by a t -value of 17.60, emphasizes the strong connection between elevated minimum temperatures and increased malaria prevalence. This observation aligns with existing research, which indicates that temperature is a vital factor in the development and longevity of malaria-carrying mosquitoes. According to (19), warmer temperatures speed up the lifecycle of *Anopheles* mosquitoes, thereby heightening the chances of malaria transmission. (20) also discovered that temperature affects the abundance and distribution of mosquito populations, with warmer conditions promoting their growth and reproduction. This finding underscores the pivotal role of minimum temperature as a significant environmental factor in the dynamics of malaria transmission and reinforces the necessity for proactive strategies in areas forecasted to experience temperature rises due to climate change. As highlighted by the research, comprehending and alleviating the impacts of temperature on malaria transmission may be crucial in tackling the disease burden among vulnerable groups.

The maximum temperature exhibits a significant and negative correlation with malaria cases, indicated by a coefficient of -0.0099 (p -value = 0.0000). This implies that for each unit increase in maximum temperature, the expected number of malaria cases decreases slightly by about 0.0099 units, assuming all other variables remain constant. The narrow 95% confidence interval, which spans from -0.0119 to -0.0079, suggests a precise and dependable estimate of this effect. The notable statistical significance, evidenced by a large absolute t -value, further supports the strength of this negative relationship. These findings imply that elevated maximum temperatures may create less suitable conditions for malaria transmission, potentially due to their impact on the biology of the vectors or parasites. Recent studies have emphasized the intricate relationship between temperature and malaria transmission. For instance, (21) discovered that while moderate temperature increases can speed up the development of mosquitoes and the maturation of parasites, extreme high temperatures can impede malaria transmission by decreasing mosquito survival and affecting parasite development. Furthermore, (22) also concluded that excessively high temperatures could surpass the thermal limits of both *Anopheles* mosquitoes and malaria parasites, thus restricting transmission. Additionally, (23) noted that in regions where maximum temperatures consistently exceed 32°C (89.6°F), there may be detrimental effects on mosquito fertility and lifespan. At these elevated temperatures, mosquitoes might not survive long enough to transmit malaria, and their reproductive capacity can also be compromised. Often, temperatures that exceed this limit are regarded as being outside the ideal range for malaria transmission. This observation reinforces the general agreement that extreme heat adversely affects malaria transmission, whereas moderate warmth facilitates the life cycle of both vectors and parasites. This highlights the significance of temperature in the dynamics of malaria, where minimum and maximum temperatures may differentially influence transmission risks. While minimum temperatures create favorable conditions for malaria transmission, extreme maximum temperatures seem to have a mitigating effect, possibly indicating biological constraints on both vectors and parasites. As climate change continues to alter temperature trends, these divergent effects underscore the necessity for nuanced malaria control strategies that take into account both low and high temperature extremes.

Our analysis indicates a strong and statistically significant positive correlation between vegetation cover and malaria incidence, evidenced by a coefficient of 0.3240. This suggests that regions with denser vegetation are more likely to see higher numbers of malaria cases. This relationship is further validated by a t -value of 16.59 and a p -value of 0.0000, signifying that the observed correlation is highly improbable to be random. The 95% confidence interval, which ranges from 0.2857 to 0.3623, is narrow, emphasizing the accuracy and reliability of this estimate. These results are consistent with a broader body of literature that underscores the important role that environmental factors play in influencing malaria transmission dynamics. As highlighted by (24), vegetation can affect the abundance and distribution of *Anopheles* mosquitoes by providing essential habitats, such as shaded areas near water sources for breeding, as well as offering refuge and nutrition that enhance mosquito survival and reproduction. In tropical regions, vegetation cover can

help create microclimates that are more favorable for mosquito proliferation, thereby increasing the likelihood of malaria transmission(25).

Additionally, the impact of vegetation extends beyond simply creating ideal mosquito habitats; it may also modify the interactions between humans and vectors. A study by (26), indicates that denser vegetation can raise the chances of human exposure to malaria-carrying mosquitoes, as increased plant growth may result in more frequent contact between mosquitoes and humans. Consequently, the relationship observed may be partially attributed to the fact that greater vegetation density not only promotes mosquito survival but also heightens the potential for human-vector interactions, which is crucial for the transmission of malaria.

The analysis emphasizes the crucial impact of environmental and climatic variables, especially minimum temperature and vegetation cover, on malaria occurrence. Both minimum temperature and vegetation cover act as strong positive predictors, influencing the development of mosquitoes and parasites, while vegetation cover reflects the suitability of habitats for mosquitoes. Conversely, maximum temperature shows a negative correlation, indicating that extreme heat may hinder mosquito survival and affect transmission dynamics. Although theoretically significant, rainfall was not closely linked to malaria incidence, highlighting the complex nature of its influence, which hinges on the equilibrium between creating and eliminating breeding grounds. This indicates that rainfall by itself might not be a dependable predictor of malaria risk unless other factors are taken into account. The presence of overdispersion and variability at the district level emphasizes the significance of local elements such as access to healthcare, socioeconomic factors, and environmental conditions in the dynamics of malaria. This underscores the necessity for data specific to each district and customized strategies. These conclusions underline the necessity for strong statistical models that address overdispersion and regional variability, which can improve predictions of malaria risk and aid in implementing more effective prevention measures. Additional research is required to investigate how climatic and socioeconomic factors interact in the transmission of malaria.

5. Conclusion

The regression analysis underscores the critical role of environmental and climatic factors in malaria transmission dynamics. Minimum temperature and NDVI emerged as significant positive predictors of malaria cases, while maximum temperature showed a negative association. Rainfall, although a theoretically important factor, did not demonstrate a significant effect in this context.

These findings highlight the complexity of malaria transmission, where different factors interact in intricate ways. Moreover, district-level variability emphasizes the importance of considering localized factors when designing malaria control strategies.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

I acknowledge the Government of Uganda through Makerere University Research and Innovations Fund (MAKRIF) for collaboration.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There were no Conflict of interest for this work

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval was sought from Mulago Hospital Research and Ethics Committee under the number (MHREC-2910). Administrative approval was obtained from Makerere University and the Ministry of Health before data was obtained from the Ministry.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Funding

There was no funding for this study.

References

- [1] Organization WH. World malaria report 2023. World Health Organization; 2023.
- [2] Sanna A, Lambert Y, Jimeno Maroto I, Galindo MS, Plessis L, Bardon T, et al. CUREMA project: a further step towards malaria elimination among hard-to-reach and mobile populations. *Malar J* [Internet]. 2024;23(1):271. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-024-05040-8>
- [3] Karschney LJ, Karschney LJ. ©Copyright 2024 Laura Jacquelyn Karschney. 2024;
- [4] Kolawole EO, Ayeni ET, Abolade SA, Ugwu SE, Awoyinka TB, Ofeh AS, et al. Malaria endemicity in sub-Saharan Africa: Past and present issues in public health. *Microbes Infect Dis*. 2023;4(1):242–51.
- [5] Abdishu M, Gobena T, Damena M, Abdi H, Birhanu A. Determinants of Malaria Morbidity Among School-Aged Children Living in East Hararghe Zone, Oromia, Ethiopia: A Community-Based Case–Control Study. *Pediatr Heal Med Ther*. 2022;Volume 13(April):183–93.
- [6] Venkatesan P. The 2023 WHO World malaria report. *The Lancet Microbe*. 2024;5(3):e214.
- [7] Sarfo JO, Amoadu M, Kordorwu PY, Adams AK, Gyan TB, Osman AG, et al. Malaria amongst children under five in sub-Saharan Africa: a scoping review of prevalence, risk factors and preventive interventions. *Eur J Med Res*. 2023;28(1):80.
- [8] Kooko R, Wafula ST, Orishaba P. Socioeconomic determinants of malaria prevalence among under five children in Uganda: Evidence from 2018-19 Uganda Malaria Indicator Survey. *J Vector Borne Dis*. 2023;60(1):38–48.
- [9] Ahmed A. An estimation of Severe Malaria prevalence in Children aged 0-59 months in Uganda A Secondary Analysis of Uganda's Malaria Indicator Survey 2019. 2019;
- [10] 2018-19 Uganda Malaria Indicator Survey (UMIS) Atlas of Key Indicators. 2018;
- [11] Castellani JS. Delayed access to care for childhood malaria: Financial determinants and economic consequences. 2020;
- [12] Joachimu M. Economic Costs of Malaria Infection and their Impact on Labour Productivity in Shinyanga. The Open University of Tanzania; 2020.
- [13] Ampaire R. Socio economic and behavioral aspects of malaria and its control among children under 5 years of age In Nsiika Health Centre Iv. 2018;
- [14] Namango IH. Monitoring and control of" Anopheles" vectors in the context of residual malaria transmission in Ulanga, Tanzania. *University_of_Basel_Associated_Institution*; 2024.
- [15] Pandey RK, Dubey AK, Sharma S, Rani C. Climate Change and Zoonotic Diseases: Malaria, Plague, Dengue, and Encephalitis. In: *Emerging Pandemics*. CRC Press; 2023. p. 81–98.
- [16] Megersa DM, Luo XS. Effects of Climate Change on Malaria Risk to Human Health: A Review. *Atmosphere (Basel)*. 2025;16(1):71.
- [17] Agyekum TP, Botwe PK, Arko-Mensah J, Issah I, Acquah AA, Hogarh JN, et al. A systematic review of the effects of temperature on Anopheles mosquito development and survival: implications for malaria control in a future warmer climate. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(14):7255.
- [18] Hsiao C. *Analysis of panel data*. Cambridge university press; 2022.
- [19] Yadav N, Upadhyay RK. Global effect of climate change on seasonal cycles, vector population and rising challenges of communicable diseases: a review. *J Atmos Sci Res*. 2023;6(1).
- [20] Chandra G, Mukherjee D. Effect of climate change on mosquito population and changing pattern of some diseases transmitted by them. In: *Advances in animal experimentation and modeling*. Elsevier; 2022. p. 455–60.
- [21] Fall P, Diouf I, Deme A, Diouf S, Sene D, Sultan B, et al. Enhancing Understanding of the Impact of Climate Change on Malaria in West Africa Using the Vector-Borne Disease Community Model of the International Center for Theoretical Physics (VECTRI) and the Bias-Corrected Phase 6 Coupled Model Intercomparison Proj. *Microbiol Res (Pavia)*. 2023;14(4):2148–80.

- [22] Chaves LSM, de Sousa TM, Penha LCF, Hacon SS. Malaria in the Amazon Basin: how climate change and natural disasters create new challenges for an old disease. In: Planetary health approaches to understand and control vector-borne diseases. Wageningen Academic; 2023. p. 54–91.
- [23] Orondo PW, Wang X, Lee MC, Nyanjom SG, Atieli H, Ondeto BM, et al. Habitat diversity, stability, and productivity of malaria vectors in irrigated and nonirrigated ecosystems in western Kenya. *J Med Entomol.* 2023;60(1):202–12.
- [24] Tsegaye A, Demissew A, Hawaria D, Abossie A, Getachew H, Habtamu K, et al. Anopheles larval habitats seasonality and environmental factors affecting larval abundance and distribution in Arjo-Didessa sugar cane plantation, Ethiopia. *Malar J [Internet].* 2023;22(1):1–12. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-023-04782-1>
- [25] Abigail Nana Afia Yeboah. Investigating the impact of changing environments on mosquito-borne diseases, through the lens of alterations in vegetation and human-driven landscape modifications. *World J Adv Res Rev.* 2023;18(2):1440–54.
- [26] Sertić Perić M, Dražina T, Žutinić P, Rubinić J, Kuczyńska-Kippen N, Zhang C, et al. Ecological Dynamics and Conservation Strategies for Mediterranean Salt Marshes: Insights from a Pilot Study of Biodiversity and Environmental Drivers in the Palud Marsh, Croatia. *Sustain.* 2024;16(23).